

Survey 2

The survey, conducted among 800 households as part of a pricing experiment, is detailed in the following paper: *Hofmann, Matthias, and Turid Siebenbrunner. 'A Rich Dataset of Hourly Residential Electricity Consumption Data and Survey Answers from the iFlex Dynamic Pricing Experiment'. Data in Brief 50, No. 109571 (1 October 2023).*
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2023.109571>.

The survey data are published at Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/8248802>

This document is published at Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/11580541>

Question Aq1_1: Have there been any major changes in your household that may have affected your electricity consumption during February this year? No

(IF Question Aq1_1 = Yes)

Question Aq1_2: Have there been any major changes in your household that may have affected your electricity consumption during February this year? Yes, bought an electric car

(IF Question Aq1_1 = Yes)

Question Aq1_3: Have there been any major changes in your household that may have affected your electricity consumption during February this year? Yes, bought new equipment for room heating (e.g. heat pump or additional heaters)

(IF Question Aq1_1 = Yes)

Question Aq1_4: Have there been any major changes in your household that may have affected your electricity consumption during February this year? Yes, have got a shared solution for heating or district heating

(IF Question Aq1_1 = Yes)

Question Aq1_5: Have there been any major changes in your household that may have affected your electricity consumption during February this year? Yes, have got water based heating system

(IF Question Aq1_1 = Yes)

Question Aq1_6: Have there been any major changes in your household that may have affected your electricity consumption during February this year? Yes, have insulated my home or made other improvements that reduce heat loss from the home

(IF Question Aq1_1 = Yes)

Question Aq1_7: Have there been any major changes in your household that may have affected your electricity consumption during February this year? Yes, have installed solar cells

(IF Question Aq1_1 = Yes)

Question Aq1_8: Have there been any major changes in your household that may have affected your electricity consumption during February this year? Yes, we were more or fewer residents than in January

(IF Question Aq1_1 = Yes)

Question Aq1_9: Have there been any major changes in your household that may have affected your electricity consumption during February this year? Yes, was at home in February due to corona virus

(IF Question Aq1_1 = Yes)

Question Aq1_10: Have there been any major changes in your household that may have affected your electricity consumption during February this year? Yes, other:

Question Aq2N1: Imagine that you undertake measures to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home. What consequences do you think the following measures would have for you? Turn off heating in unused rooms

Question Aq2N2: Imagine that you undertake measures to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home. What consequences do you think the following measures would have for you?
 Lower the indoor temperature by 2 degrees celsius

Question Aq2N3: Imagine that you undertake measures to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home. What consequences do you think the following measures would have for you?
 Change time schedule on time-controlled thermostats

Question Aq2N4: Imagine that you undertake measures to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home. What consequences do you think the following measures would have for you?
Use wood stove instead of electric heating

Question Aq2N5: Imagine that you undertake measures to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home. What consequences do you think the following measures would have for you?
Shift electric car charging to other hours

Question Aq2N6: Imagine that you undertake measures to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home. What consequences do you think the following measures would have for you?
Charge your electric car more often elsewhere than at home

Question Aq2N7: Imagine that you undertake measures to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home. What consequences do you think the following measures would have for you?
Shift showering and bathing to other hours

Question Aq2N8: Imagine that you undertake measures to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home. What consequences do you think the following measures would have for you? Shower shorter periods / take fewer baths

Question Aq3_1: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home? Lower electricity bill

Question Aq3_2: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home? Electricity-saving measures that are easy to do

Question Aq3_3: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home? Electricity-saving measures that happen automatically so that I don't have to think about it

Question Aq3_4: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home? Electricity-saving measures that do not affect the comfort at home

Question Aq3_5: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home? Test new technology to control electricity consumption

Question Aq3_6: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home? Less negative impact on nature and climate from electricity production and electricity grid

Question Aq3_7: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home? Reduce the need for electricity grid development of society

Question Aq3_8: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home? Other:

Question Aq3_9: Could any of the following motivate you to reduce your electricity consumption for 4 consecutive hours some days in winter, when it is cold outside and you are at home? No one, do not want to or do not can change my electricity consumption

(IF Question Aq3_9 = No one, do not want to or do not can change ...)

Question Aq4_1: Why do you not want to reduce your electricity consumption? Have no ability to reduce electricity consumption

(IF Question Aq3_9 = No one, do not want to or do not can change ...)

Question Aq4_2: Why do you not want to reduce your electricity consumption? Do not know how I can reduce electricity consumption

(IF Question Aq3_9 = No one, do not want to or do not can change ...)

Question Aq4_3: Why do you not want to reduce your electricity consumption? Consequences are too large

(IF Question Aq3_9 = No one, do not want to or do not can change ...)

Question Aq4_4: Why do you not want to reduce your electricity consumption? Do not want to spend time on this

(IF Question Aq3_9 = No one, do not want to or do not can change ...)

Question Aq4_5: Why do you not want to reduce your electricity consumption? My electricity costs are not that high

(IF Question Aq3_9 = No one, do not want to or do not can change ...)

Question Aq4_6: Why do you not want to reduce your electricity consumption? Other:

Question Aq5N1: If you were to change your electricity consumption pattern, how likely is it that you would do the following ...? Changed daily routines so that my electricity consumption is changed permanently

Question Aq5N2: If you were to change your electricity consumption pattern, how likely is it that you would do the following ...? Invested in equipment so that the change in electricity consumption happens automatically so that I don't have to do anything

Question Aq5N3: If you were to change your electricity consumption pattern, how likely is it that you would do the following ...? Changed the electricity consumption a few times a year after I had been notified in advance

Question Aq5N4: If you were to change your electricity consumption pattern, how likely is it that you would do the following ...? Other measures

Question Aq6: Approximately how large total electricity expenses (incl. all taxes, grid fee, etc.) had your household on average per month during the last year?

Question Aq7: Approximately how much did your household pay per kWh of electricity (incl. all taxes, grid fee, etc.) on average during the last year?

Question Aq8: How much money do you need to save in one day, to be interested in reducing your electricity consumption by 10% for 4 consecutive hours with high electricity prices on a winter day?

Question Aq9: How much money do you need to save per month, to be interested in reducing your electricity consumption by 10% for 4 consecutive hours per day, 10 days in the winter months?

Question Aq10: How much money do you need to save per month, to be interested in reducing your electricity consumption by 10% for 4 consecutive hours on all weekdays during the winter months?

Question Aq11: How much money do you need to save per month if you could switch to a cheaper electricity supplier?

Question Aq12: Imagine that you could get paid to reduce your electricity consumption. How much money do you need to earn per month, to be interested in reducing your electricity consumption by 10% for 4 consecutive hours per day, 10 days in the winter months?

Question Aq13: How much money do you need to save per month on average in the next few years, in order to think about buying electricity-saving equipment that costs NOK 5,000? The equipment will reduce your electricity bill by automatically controlling parts of your consumption during the day without inconvenience to you.

Question Aq14: Would you use a free information service that notifies you when the price of electricity the next day would be over a given level for a few hours?

(IF Question Aq14 = Yes)

Question Aq15: How much higher has the electricity price to be compared to an average electricity price of 1 NOK/kWh so that you want to be notified?

Question Aq16: We want to find out how information about electricity costs can best be communicated to households. Which of the following formulations / illustrations gives you the best opportunity to understand how much you can save at different times?

(IF part of a treatment group / not control group, for all following questions)

Question Aq17: Your household participated in Statnett's price experiment in February and March 2020. We are interested in how you experienced the experiment and have therefore some questions. Did you actively follow the price signals given during the experiment?

(IF Question Aq17 = Yes OR Sometimes)

Question Aq18: Did you undertake measures in your household to reduce or shift electricity consumption during hours with high prices?

(IF Question Aq18 = Yes)

Question Aq19_1: What measures did you undertake? Turned off electric heating in unused rooms

(IF Question Aq18 = Yes)

Question Aq19_2: What measures did you undertake? Lowered indoor temperature

(IF Question Aq18 = Yes)

Question Aq19_3: What measures did you undertake? Changed schedule on time-controlled thermostats

(IF Question Aq18 = Yes)

Question Aq19_4: What measures did you undertake? Used wood oven rather instead of electric heating

(IF Question Aq18 = Yes)

Question Aq19_5: What measures did you undertake? Shifted electric car charging to hours with lower electricity prices

(IF Question Aq18 = Yes)

Question Aq19_6: What measures did you undertake? Charged my electric car more often elsewhere than at home

(IF Question Aq18 = Yes)

Question Aq19_7: What measures did you undertake? Shifted showering and bathing to hours with lower electricity prices

(IF Question Aq18 = Yes)

Question Aq19_8: What measures did you undertake? Showered for shorter periods / took fewer baths

(IF Question Aq18 = Yes)

Question Aq19_9: What measures did you undertake? Other:

(IF Question Aq18 = No)

Question Aq20_1: Why did you not undertake such measures? Did not have time to find out what measures I/we could undertake

(IF Question Aq18 = No)

Question Aq20_2: Why did you not undertake such measures? Little time in everyday life made it difficult to undertake measures

(IF Question Aq18 = No)

Question Aq20_3: Why did you not undertake such measures? Was not home

(IF Question Aq18 = No)

Question Aq20_4: Why did you not undertake such measures? The disadvantages of possible measures would be too great

(IF Question Aq18 = No)

Question Aq20_5: Why did you not undertake such measures? Difficult to understand what I/we could have done

(IF Question Aq18 = No)

Question Aq20_6: Why did you not undertake such measures? The opportunity to earn money was too small

(IF Question Aq18 = No)

Question Aq20_7: Why did you not undertake such measures? My electricity consumption is fine as it is

(IF Question Aq18 = No)

Question Aq20_8: Why did you not undertake such measures? We disagreed / had different needs, and therefore did not undertake anything

(IF Question Aq18 = No)

Question Aq20_9: Why did you not undertake such measures? The person who received the price signal is not the one who most often deals with tasks related to electricity use

(IF Question Aq18 = No)

Question Aq20_10: Why did you not undertake such measures? Other:

(IF Question Aq17 = No)

Question Aq21_1: Why did you not actively follow the price signals given during the experiment? Did not have time to check the prices

(IF Question Aq17 = No)

Question Aq21_2: Why did you not actively follow the price signals given during the experiment? Was not home

(IF Question Aq17 = No)

Question Aq21_3: Why did you not actively follow the price signals given during the experiment? Did not have time to undertake measures to react to the prices anyway

(IF Question Aq17 = No)

Question Aq21_4: Why did you not actively follow the price signals given during the experiment? The disadvantages of possible measures would be too great

(IF Question Aq17 = No)

Question Aq21_5: Why did you not actively follow the price signals given during the experiment? Difficult to understand what I/we could have done

(IF Question Aq17 = No)

Question Aq21_6: Why did you not actively follow the price signals given during the experiment? The opportunity to earn money was too small

(IF Question Aq17 = No)

Question Aq21_7: Why did you not actively follow the price signals given during the experiment? My electricity consumption is fine as it is

(IF Question Aq17 = No)

Question Aq21_8: Why did you not actively follow the price signals given during the experiment? Other:

Question Aq22: Do you want to meet researchers? Households that finish the interview receive a gift card of NOK 500. If it okay for you, would you like to be contacted by these researchers via the same email that was used for this survey to arrange an interview at your home?

